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A REVIEW ON ANTICIPATED BREAKTHROUGH TECHNOLOGIES OF 21ST CENTURY

by

P. Sreeramana Aithal | Professor | Srinivas Institute of Management Studies | Pandeshwar,
Mangalore, India | psaithal@gmail.com

&

P. Shubhrajyotsna Aithal | Associate Professor | Srinivas College, Pandeshwar | Mangalore,
India | psaithal@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

This review discuss strategic management of thirteen most anticipated possible technology breakthroughs of 21st century which are substantially affect the life style of living beings in the world like (1) Nanotechnology based human life comfort, (2) High speed computation through optical computers, (3) Embedded Intelligence, (4) HIV Antivirus, (5) Pseudo Senses - Sensation of existence through virtual reality and through artificial environment, (6) Off Planet Production in micro-gravity, (7) Protein Maps to know how many active genes are coding for proteins in living being, (8) Customized Kids which are used for Customization of physical and mental ability of children, (9) Development of Chameleon Chips which are reconfigurable photonic circuits using the idea of optical solitons, (10) Flying cars through manipulation of gravitational force, (11) Immortality through nano-bio-technology & stem cell research, (12) Fractal Models for fragmented geometry shapes, and (13) Space travel for everybody. The paper also discuss the effect of these technology breakthroughs and possible changes in lifestyle of people in the society and its contribution in solving many basic problems of human beings on the earth by means of systematic management such breakthrough technologies

KEYWORDS: MSMEs, Problems, Outstanding Credit, Financing.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Every rational person in this world constantly aims to improve his standard of living. Forecasting the future technologies is important for dreamers who hope to innovate better tools and techniques and through such research to achieve breakthroughs for the mainstream people who expect to benefit from such new and improved technologies. Many inventions are born in the lab and never enters into the consumer market, while others evolve beyond the expectation of putting good regulations on their use. Since the beginning of the 21st century, mankind has made tremendous strides and struggles in developing new technologies and manage them efficiently and effectively to improve the quality of life. While machines can replicate many movements and actions of humans, the next challenge lies in teaching them to think for themselves and react to changing conditions [1]. For example, the field of artificial intelligence will one day give machines the ability to think analytically. Exploring space will also push genetic research. It is predicted that travelling to and living in other planets such as Mars with extreme cold temperatures and toxic atmosphere will require genetic changes through gene therapies. Sending humans into space without genetic modification would be impractical. However, we need breakthroughs to achieve this glowing future. Similarly, many anticipated technology breakthroughs are expected to change the lifestyle, comfort and thinking of human beings in near future [2]. Will these breakthroughs happen? Experts believe technologies will develop at lightning speeds during this century. Between 2015 and 2035, we could see more breakthroughs than in the last 200 years. From 2035-to-2050, advances might outpace all of human history, and from 2050-to-2100, massive discoveries beyond the wildest imaginings of science fiction could appear. As we trek into this future, aided by technologies we cannot even imagine today, it's easy to predict and believe that sometime during the 22nd century, more humans will live in space than on Earth. This review paper discuss thirteen, the most anticipated possible technology breakthroughs of 21st century which are substantially affect the life style of living beings in the world provided they are managed properly by utilizing the advantages of them for human prosperity. These technologies are (1) Nanotechnology based human life comfort, (2) High speed computation through optical computers, (3) Embedded Intelligence, (4) HIV Antivirus, (5) Pseudo Senses - Sensation of existence through virtual reality and through artificial environment, (6) Off Planet Production in micro-gravity, (7) Protein Maps to know how many active genes are coding for proteins in living being, (8) Customized Kids which are used for Customization of physical and mental ability of children, (9) Development of Chameleon Chips which are reconfigurable photonic circuits using the idea of optical solitons, (10) Flying cars through manipulation of gravitational force, (11) Immortality through nano-bio-technology & stem cell research, (12) Fractal Models for fragmented geometry shapes, and (13) Space travel for everybody. The effect of these technology breakthroughs, their effective management, possible changes in lifestyle of people in the society and its contribution in solving many basic & advanced problems of human beings on the earth are also discussed.

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II. SOME ANTICIPATED BREAKTHROUGH TECHNOLOGIES OF THIS CENTURY

Based on various factors which solves basic needs and advanced comfortability of human life, the technology breakthrough model consisting of nanotechnology and interrelated technologies and a set of independent technologies are derived by a qualitative data collection instrument namely focus group method [3, 4]. The block diagram of such a system is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 : Block diagram to represent interrelated & independent technologies.

The anticipated breakthrough technologies are divided into two groups and listed below :

➤ Interrelated Technologies :

1. Nanotechnology
2. Optical Computation
3. Embedded Intelligence
4. Chameleon Chips
5. Flying cars
6. Immortality through nano-bio-technology
7. Space travel

➤ Independent Technologies :

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1. HIV Antivirus
2. Pseudo Senses
3. Off Planet Production
4. Protein Maps
5. Customized Kids
6. Fractal Models

III. MANAGING BREAKTHROUGH TECHNOLOGIES

1. Nanotechnology:

Nanotechnology is the manipulation of matter at a scale of 1 to 100 nanometers. Using nanotechnology we can control molecules at an atomic level and create materials with unique properties. Fundamentally the properties of materials can be changed by nanotechnology. We can arrange molecules in a way that they do not normally occur in nature. The mechanical, material strength, electronic and optical properties of materials can all be altered using nanotechnology. There are different means like lithography, self-assembly, bottom-up methods to manipulate nanomaterials. Nanotechnology is the first worldwide research initiative of the 21st century.

As general purpose and enabling technologies, nanotechnologies reveal commercialization processes, from small to large firms in collaboration with public sector research, and which lead to changing patterns of industrial organization which influence public policy initiatives to foster their development [5-7]. Nanotechnologies are not only general purpose technologies – they are also technologies that enable the creation of new devices and new ways to improve the quality of life. Nanotechnologies are used in existing industries and new research areas are developed within existing areas, transforming them from microelectronics to nano-electronics, from photonics to nano-photonics, from biotechnologies to nano-bio-technologies, and from energy to nano energy. Business firms are exploring new ways to address consumer needs, new business models based on the changes nanotechnologies could enable in existing industries. Huge amount of investments in nanotechnology to support scientific and technological researches, the creation of technological and industrial platforms and infrastructures have led to more than two million articles related to nanotechnologies being published, and over one million applications patents were lodged.

Nanotechnology has the potential to change every part of our lives. Nanotechnology affects all materials like metals, ceramics, polymers, organics and biomaterials. In the coming decade nanotechnology will have an enormous impact in all areas of life. Future advances could change our approaches to manufacturing, electronics, IT & communications technology, space technology, agriculture & food technology, renewable energy, biotechnology and medicine,

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making previous technology redundant and leading to applications which could not have been developed or even thought about, without this new approach. Nanotechnology will play major role in solving all the problems of humans like food, drinking water, energy, health, environment and many other areas including life span expansion.

Some of the Application areas of Nanotechnology are :

- **Medicine** : This include drug delivery, therapy techniques, diagnostic techniques, antimicrobial techniques, cell repair, cancer detection & curing, gene therapy, nanotech in regenerative medicine & tissue engineering, life span extension etc.
- **Electronics** : This include development of nanotransistors, nanogates, nanodevice based integrated circuits, nanoemmissive display panels, nanomemories, nanowires, nanophotonic devices, Nano-optical computers etc.
- **Agriculture & Food** : This include contamination sensor, antimicrobial packaging, enhanced nutrient delivery, green packaging, pesticide reduction, tracking & brand protection, texture, food flavor, bacteria and virus identification & elimination etc.
- **Cleaner Air & Water** : This include pollution control, nanotech windmill blades, nanostructure membranes, water cleaning nanotechnology devices, nanoparticle catalysts, removal of carbon dioxide from industrial smoke stacks, nanotubes as the pores in reverse osmosis membranes, nanotech based water purifiers etc.
- **Batteries & Fuel Cells** : This include nanostructure fuel cells, hydrogen nanofuel cells, nanotech alternative fuel cells, long life high storage capacity fast rechargeable nanotech batteries etc.
- **Automobile & Space Technology** : This include nanomaterial based automobile parts, space elevators, weight reduction in spaceships and spacesuits, solar power satellites, bio-nano-machines for space applications, new breed of robots to explore the planets etc.
- **Sensors** : This include chemical sensors, MEMS based sensors, nano-hydrogen sensors, Nanocantilevers etc.
- **Consumer Products** : Devices like sporting goods, fabrics & textiles, cosmetics, skin care products, sunscreens, flame retardants, nanocleaning products, nanopaints, and any other products based on nanotechnology.
- **Renewable Energy** : This include inexpensive solar cells, devices for capturing, storage, & use of energy optimally.
- **Defense** : This include concepts like nano for the soldier, nano for defense vehicles, nano for aeronautics, nano for naval vessels, nanotechnology for weapon systems, nano for satellites, nano for logistics, nano for security, nano for military operations at land, nano for

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- military operations in the air, nano for military operations at sea, nanotechnology for urban operations etc.
- **Civil & Mechanical Engineering Manufacturing** : This include nano-material technology, nano-processing technology, nano-assembly technology, nano-coating technology, and nano-measurement technology in mechanical manufacturing. This also include nanorobotics, Micro-ElectroMechanical Systems (MEMS) for accelerometer chips, inkjet nozzles, pressure sensors, microphones, RF switches, gyroscope, oscillators etc.
- **Building Materials** : This include various future building materials like aerogels, nanotube mixed concrete, nanopaints, building integrated photovoltaic's, nanophotonic materials as building cooler. nanotechnology on construction, and fire protection etc.

Timeline for nanotechnology innovations is predicted in various literatures is as follows :

- Passive Nanostructures (2000-2015) : Nanomaterials, including nanotubes and nanolayers.
- Active Nanostructures (2015-2020) : Change their state during use, responding in predicable ways to the environment.
- Systems of Nanosystems (2020-2035) : assemblies of nanotools work together to achieve a final goal.
- Molecular Nanosystems (2035-2050) : involves the intelligent design of molecular and atomic devices, leading to “unprecedented understanding and control over the basic building blocks of all natural and man-made things.
- The Singularity (2050 and beyond): growth rate in NT applications become almost infinite.

The ability to see nano-sized materials has opened up a world of possibilities in variety of industries and scientific endeavors. Because nanotechnology is essentially a set of techniques that allow manipulation of properties at a very small scale, it can have many applications in all parts of life. Nanotechnology is viewed broadly as many technologies over time are expected to generate numerous new products and applications. Products of nanotechnology are diverse and growing exponentially. It is believed that nanotechnology can be used to significantly extend the human lifespan or produce replicator- like devices that can create almost anything from simple raw materials. The applications of nanotechnology identified in different areas provides lots of business opportunities which include health & medicine, electronics & photonics, food & food preservation, fuel cells & batteries, efficient solar cells, space travels, fuels, better air quality, cleaner drinking water, chemical sensors, sporting goods, fabric, cleaning products, energy, environment, and even life span increase. Management of nanotechnology research involves promotion and support of an idea to reality to make some very fine and small-scaled tools called nanotools. These tools have to be assembled at the molecular level in order to

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perform work at the nano level. The work of nanotechnology is so specialized that the tools need to be modeled and made specifically for each job. Handling the tools involves careful and minute planning so that those skilled in molecular nanotechnology will be in high demand in the workforce [8-9].

Anticipated breakthrough in nanotechnology will soon radically change our lives and entire world. Researchers and policy makers from around the world believe that nanotechnology is about to radically transform world economies, improve global environment, and provide a new understanding of what it means to be human.

2. High Speed Computing through Optical Computers :

High performance computing through optical computing is the science of making computing work better using optics and related technologies. Optics has the ability to solve hectic problems in computing hardware. With the growth of computing technology the need of high performance computers (HPC) has significantly increased [10]. Even though lot of research is taking place in laboratories, optical computing research has so far failed to come out of the lab in the form of a general purpose device. The construction of optical subsystems directly on-chip, with the same lithographic tools as the surrounding electronics has been made possible by the advances in these tools, which can now create features significantly smaller than the optical wavelength [11].

The need for optical technology arrives from the fact that present day computers are limited by the time response and speed of electronic circuits. A solid transmission medium limits both the speed and volume of signals, as well as generating heat that damages components. These constraints have led scientists to seek answers in light itself. Light does not have the time response limitations of electronics, does not need insulators, and can even send dozens or hundreds of photon signal streams simultaneously using different color frequencies. They have low-loss transmission and provide large bandwidth. By replacing electrons and wires with photons, fiber optics, crystals, thin films and mirrors, researchers are hoping to build a new generation of computers that work several million times faster than conventional computers [12].

Some of the advantages of optical computers are listed below :

- **High Performance** : The performance of an optical computer in an advanced stage should be several orders of magnitude higher than the conventional computer.
- **High Parallelism** : Another key to fasten up optical computers is to compute with higher parallelism. This implies higher performance and higher bandwidth.

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- **Low Energy Consumption** : Optical computers have the potential to be more power-saving than conventional ones.
- **Less Heat Dissipation** : In optical computers lasers are used as light sources. Those concentrated light beams only consist of a small spectrum of different wavelengths. Depending on the field of application lasers have different needs of energy and produce heat to a greater or lesser extent. Optical computers could be smaller because there is no need for a fan or free spaces for air circulation.
- **Low Noise** : Conventional computers produce noise due to rotating fans and drives. Optical computers could be almost noiseless since no fan will be needed. Light sources (e.g. lasers) can be cooled with passive coolers and heat pipes built out of aluminum or copper. Those passive coolers evacuate heat silently.
- **Flexibility Layout** : In optical components the distance of communication does not matter. Once the signal is in an optical fiber it does not matter whether the signal runs 1 meter or 1000 meters. Because of the low damping long-range communication is possible. Still the data rate is very high and there is no crosstalk. So the optical computer technology has the potential to change the shape and layout of computers fundamentally.
- **Low Loss in Communication** : The communication with optical fibers is almost lossless due to the total internal reflection. So amplifying the signal is not or only rarely needed. Furthermore a higher bandwidth is possible, optical communication is insensible to electromagnetic interfering fields and it is more tap-proof. For high performance communication fiber optics are used.
- **Less Wear** : Wear normally occurs at mechanically moving parts. In optical computers fans will not be required. An optical processor does not heat up due to internal friction of the electrons like a conventional computer does. Additionally new technologies for mass storages in the form of holograms or on molecular basis is possible. Those forms do not need fast rotating parts and do not wear out. It is sure that the scientists of 21st century will make a breakthrough by developing a suitable model and realize such model using suitable materials and components, and algorithms to realize both optical and quantum computers in the society.

3. Embedded Intelligence :

The ability of a product, process or service to reflect on its own operational performance, usage load, or in relation to the end-user or environment in terms of satisfactory experience and smart improvement is characterised as Embedded Intelligence. This improvement through self-reflection, facilitated by information collected by sensors and processed locally or remotely, must be considered from the design stage such as to improve the product features, enhance the

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product lifetime and performance, increase quality of process or service delivery, or ensure customer satisfaction and market acceptance [13-16]. Embedded intelligence aims at delivering smarter products, systems or services to industry through their integration and purposeful use for a given application. Embedded intelligence (EI) system/service application contains various components/processes which include design for EI, intelligent software, packaging & interconnect, manufacturing solutions and/or system services.

The integration of embedded processors with sensors, intelligence, wireless connectivity and other components with high level operating systems, middleware and system integration services is possible and it is predicted that over the next 10 years “IT devices for industries including medical, manufacturing, transportation, retail, communication, consumer electronics and energy will take a development direction that makes intelligent designs become a part of all of our lifestyles”. This forecasts a significant growth for embedded systems in future years. The digital devices based on embedded systems just don't have keyboards and screens, since they're buried inside stereos, vacuum cleaners, microwave ovens, and almost anything else that plugs into the wall or runs on batteries. Wireless-communications technology is wrapping the earth in layer upon layer of interconnectivity. And those tiny chips embedded in everyday gadgets will keep getting more powerful. Soon, the anonymous chips will get smart and be aware of their silicon neighbors, which is possible with the help of integrated sensors and wireless telecom systems. For example, the bedroom clock will just need to reach the phone to check on traffic patterns and flight schedules before deciding whether it should fiddle with its alarm time. Similarly when rechargeable toothbrush detects signs of a cavity, it can send signals through the electrical wiring and get in electronic daybook to consult with dentist's digital appointment book, then display a few options on the bathroom mirror. Software agents with embedded intelligence will roam the wireless Web, autonomously managing most routine business and household chores. For example, if a product-design problem come up at work, the smart-card companion in the that place will be informed, and it will activate the display circuits in the paint on the nearest wall to display instead of using an electronic fold-up display. Welcome to tomorrow's world of embedded intelligence as a breakthrough technology of 21st century [17-18].

4. HIV Antivirus :

Satisfactory and complete curing of HIV by discovering a suitable antivirus is one of the anticipated and most required technology breakthroughs of this century. With just 10 genes wrapped in a coating of protein and sugar, the virus that causes aids (left) has managed to stay several steps ahead of humanity's best efforts to control it. More than 55 million people have been infected around the world. But medicine is beginning to control this deadly scourge--with implications that go beyond aids. For instance, scientists have uncovered the wily molecular

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tricks HIV uses to slip its own genes into cells. That has enabled companies to devise drugs capable of blocking viral entry. The unprecedented research effort is also dramatically boosting our understanding of the immune system. In aids, clever new vaccines based on that knowledge are already offering the hope that the body could keep the virus in check on its own. And the aids breakthroughs will catalyze development of treatments for other diseases as well. Intensive research are going on at several laboratories to develop suitable antiviral dosage for permanent cure of HIV/AIDS [19-20]. Scientists caution that a permanent cure for aids is still a dream. But new drugs, vaccines, and a growing international commitment to fight the illness as both a health and an economic problem should finally end this epidemic--and also help improve the public health infrastructure enough to tame malaria and other terrible diseases [21].

5. Pseudo Senses :

Sensation of existence through virtual reality, by creating artificial environment is another expected breakthrough of this century, It is predicted that virtualized reality will restore the sense of shared community that people had before we began sequestering ourselves in front of TV sets and computer screens.

In pseudoscience literature one frequently encounters the claim that there are some people, called "sensitives" or psychics," who somehow can pick up the thoughts of others and even transmit their own thoughts to people who are not "sensitives." This direct mind-to-mind communication is sometimes claimed to be instantaneous, and independent of distance. It is also often claimed that all people and even domestic animals such as cats, dogs, and horses -- possess this ability to some degree, and that ordinary coincidences are in fact no ordinary, but rather mysterious demonstrations of this supposed ability. Sometimes, but rarely, specific experiments are cited as having confirmed the existence of telepathy, clairvoyance, precognition, telekinesis, or other such "supernatural" abilities in humans or animals. Furthermore, in the course of evolution many kinds of animals have developed extremely acute senses of one kind or another, compared to those of humans. Dogs have much more highly developed sense of smell than do humans; hawks and eagles, more acute eyesight; bats, much wider range of hearing, etc.

Cognitive science through virtual reality represents an awesome look into our future. New theories about functions of our brain are unfolding at increasingly rapid intervals. Some experts believe a new understanding of the brain will lead to the creation of truly intelligent machines. Others suggest far-out technologies such as "Neural Virtual Reality" (NVR). NVR takes existing virtual reality technology to the next level by pumping virtual environments directly into the brain with neural implants. Transmitted signals trick the brain into believing the body is actually participating in a simulated experience. The implant tells the brain what the body is

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hearing and how it should feel. With all sensory inputs provided by NVR, a sufficiently realistic simulation is indistinguishable from reality, much like a dream. Today, we cannot even conceive all the applications that this extreme technology could provide. However, cognitive science promises a truly "magical future" for all to enjoy [22-24].

6. Off Planet Production in Micro-Gravity :

Orbiting 220 miles above the Earth, the International Space Station offers more than just a spectacular view. It also gives scientists the chance to conduct research in the near absence of gravity. The result could be everything from new plant varieties to important new synthetic materials. Gravity, it turns out, is such a strong and pervasive force that it masks many interesting physical properties, including those related to combustion. In the space station, where gravity has only one-millionth the strength it has on Earth, hot gases do not rise, so flames are spherical and stable--and thus easier to study. Such flames can be used to create novel "combustion-synthesized" materials. One such material is a ceramic that could serve as an artificial bone. Powders are mixed and ignited to make the material, which is much more uniform when made in microgravity than when made on Earth. Researchers have also found that a rose is a rose except when it's grown in space. A rose carried aboard a 1998 shuttle flight had a different scent than roses grown on Earth. That heavenly fragrance was later synthesized on Earth and has already been used in a commercial perfume. Thus off-planet production in micro-gravity space may provide new varieties of plants, new structures & colour combinations of flowers, new breed of seeds and even new community of animals. It is anticipated that in 21st century such possibilities will be completely explored [25-28].

7. Protein maps to know how many active genes are coding for proteins in living being :

The decoding of the human genome has barely been completed but already scientists are delving into biology's next challenge: proteomics, the large-scale study of proteins. The goal is to understand the functions of the million or so proteins in the human body. With this knowledge, researchers say they can devise treatments to diagnose and eventually eliminate many diseases [29, 2].

Mapping the human proteome is a monumental task. It will require hundreds of millions of dollars in investment and untold trillions of computations. The molecular contrasts tell the whole story: The human genome is made of DNA--simple, linear molecules containing just four basic constituents. Proteins, on the other hand, are exquisitely complicated structures wrought from 20 different building blocks called amino acids. These molecules fold their hundreds of thousands of atoms into precise configurations that can perform specific cellular tasks--building cellular structures, for example, or charging into the bloodstream as disease-fighting antibodies.

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The natural origami underlying large proteins such as Factor VIII (left)--a common clotting factor in the blood--is so complex that scientists cannot yet predict the pattern, even with the help of the most powerful supercomputers. But solving the protein-folding mystery will yield insights into numerous diseases, including Parkinson's, Alzheimer's, and mad cow. And the more they learn about proteins, the closer they come to curing killers such as breast cancer and diabetes [30-34].

8. Customization of Physical and Mental Ability of Kids :

We all desire perfect lives for our children. So is there anything wrong with giving them every edge we can afford to ensure their success, including removal of genetic flaws before they're born. Deciding how and when to meddle with genes may raise the most difficult ethical questions facing humankind in the third millennium. Already, several doctors have announced efforts to attempt human cloning, making an exact genetic copy of anyone who hands over his or her DNA. Other scientists are furiously working to perfect "germline" engineering, in which a gene would be permanently removed, added, or altered in an embryo, ensuring that certain genetic traits would or would not be replicated in all future generations [35-37]. Surprisingly, cloning has already gained support from some doctors and ethicists as an infertility treatment of last resort. Germline engineering, though, raises more concerns, may sound okay for parents with deadly hereditary diseases to pluck out the offending gene from an embryo. But where might be the consequence ? Rich parents could use this technology to modify children in all sorts of ways, attempting to add genes for athletic prowess or intelligence, creating a social divide of genetic haves and have-nots. This may lead to a new race of reengineered people who might not be able to breed with those whose genetic makeup was left to chance [38-39].

9. Development of Chameleon Chips which are reconfigurable photonic circuits using the idea of optical solitons :

Some computer scientists are hatching a novel idea that could modify the internal circuitry depending upon application. This will crunch the power requirement and trim costs as well. Such an integrated circuit chip is called chameleon chip [2, 40]. Today's microprocessors carry a general-purpose design, which is both good and bad. The good thing is that the chip can run a range of programs in a computers for different jobs, such as crunching spreadsheets or editing digital photos. The bad thing is that for any one application, much of the chip's circuitry isn't needed, and the presence of those "wasted" circuits slows things down. Based on Chameleon chips idea, one set of chips, little bigger than a credit card, could do almost anything, even changing into a wireless phone. The market for such versatile marvels would be huge, and would translate into lower costs for users.

Chameleon chips would be an extension of what can already be done with field-programmable gate arrays (FPGAS). An FPGA is covered with a grid of wires. At each crossover, there's a

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switch that can be semi-permanently opened or closed by sending it a special signal. Usually the chip must first be inserted in a little box that sends the programming signals. But now, labs in Europe, Japan, and the U.S. are developing techniques to rewire FPGA-like chips and even software that can map out circuitry that's optimized for specific problems. The chips still won't change colors. But they may well colour the way we use computers in years to come [41-44].

10. Flying Cars through manipulation of Gravitational Force :

The absence of flying cars speaks to a failure of engineering or distorted incentives in the marketplace. But the humbling truth is that we don't have these vehicles because we still don't know, even in principle, how to directly manipulate gravity. Indeed, the cars missing from our skies should serve to remind us that, to a degree rarely appreciated, we have surprisingly poor control over most of nature's fundamental forces [64]. Physicists have compiled a comprehensive inventory of all the ways things can pull or push on other things, a complete itemization of nature's forces. They've found just four. The first is gravity, the force that keeps your feet on the ground. The second is electromagnetism, which is responsible for anything involving light or the arrangement of atoms. The third is the strong nuclear force, which binds protons and neutrons together inside every atom. And the fourth is the weak nuclear force, which (among other forces) helps guide the fusion reactions that power stars.

For all the power of modern science, we are masters of only one of these forces: electromagnetism. Laptops, smartphones, wirelessly connected thermostats, google glass - all our high-tech miracles exist because we've learned to control the electromagnetic force at the subtlest of levels. When it comes to electromagnetism, we have powers that are almost godlike. With the other three, we're not even close. For example, nuclear power plants rely on our remarkable knowledge of the strong and weak nuclear forces. But when all is said and done they simply use the heat generated by splitting atomic nuclei to boil water, which then spins turbines, which then generate electricity. That's not so different from a 19th-century steam engine. Compared with the precision of an electron microscope (or even a grocery-store laser scanner), our handling of nuclear forces is still at the level of slamming rocks together. The same is true of gravity. Obviously, we can make a plane fly by forcing air to flow over a wing, which generates the pressure to lift it off the ground. But the interaction of those air molecules is a result of electromagnetic forces and the fuel we use to power planes & blow rockets off the planet is a result of our understanding of chemistry, which again is a matter of electromagnetism. Thus all our ways of flying involve a heavy-handed application of the electromagnetic force through fuels and engines. The noise, the danger, the pollution and the inefficiency that accompany the current ways of flying are a testament to our crude approach to defying gravity.

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The problem is due to the fact that we don't understand gravity at its most fundamental level. Much as a seemingly smooth shoreline is actually composed of quintillions of individual sand grains, every aspect of the world - matter, energy and motion - is actually parceled into infinitesimal building blocks. The four forces that shape the world come in little packages, too. With electromagnetism and the nuclear forces, we understand how the parceled behavior, the quantum mechanics of these forces works. And the digital culture we've built rests directly on our ability to understand and manipulate electromagnetism's quantum manifestations. But with gravity we remain in the dark. We have no theory of quantum gravity and without the ability to manipulate the quantum gravitational world, we won't be gliding around in the silky hush of hover-cars anytime soon. Instead we will have to fly the old-fashioned electromagnetic way. Hence, all our technological powers, we are still constrained by the deepest structures underlying physical reality. If one force can be easily manipulated at room temperature but another requires the power of a cosmic explosion, then those are facts we just have to work with [45-48].

11. Immortality through nano-bio-technology & stem cell research :

Immortality is eternal life or the ability to live forever. Biological forms have inherent limitations which medical interventions or engineering may or may not be able to overcome. Natural selection has developed potential biological immortality in at least one species, the jellyfish. Certain scientists, futurists, and philosophers, have theorized about the immortality of the human body, and advocate that human immortality is achievable in the first few decades of the 21st century, while other advocates believe that life extension is a more achievable goal in the short term, with immortality awaiting further research breakthroughs into an indefinite future. newly developing technologies may be used to induce biological immortality in human beings. Human embryonic stem cells generated considerable excitement since they were a means of mass-producing replacement cells for the treatment of a host of degenerative diseases involving the loss or dysfunction of cells, including those in osteoarthritis, macular degeneration, diabetes, heart failure, Parkinson's disease, and numerous other disorders. The first report of the isolation of these cells marked the birth of the new field called regenerative medicine. When perfected, this technology offered the theoretical potential of rejuvenating an entire human body back to a youthful state. Hence immortality is the ultimate goal of ideal technology so that it can create an avenue for deathless situation or enhancement of human life span [49-52].

There are two ways in which nanotechnology may be able to extend our lives. One is by helping to eradicate life-threatening diseases such as cancer, and the other is by repairing damage to our bodies at the cellular level--a nano version of the fountain of youth. The most exciting possibility exists in the potential for repairing our bodies at the cellular level.

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Techniques for building nanorobots are being developed that should make the repair of our cells possible. For example, as we age, DNA in our cells is damaged by radiation or chemicals in our bodies. Nanorobots would be able to repair the damaged DNA and allow our cells to function correctly. This ability to repair DNA and other defective components in our cells goes beyond keeping us healthy: it has the potential to restore our bodies to a more youthful condition. The extension of the human lifespan could be facilitated through the removal of a substance called lipofuscin from certain types of non-dividing cells, including the brain, heart, liver, kidneys and eyes. Lipofuscin is a metabolic end product that accumulates primarily within lysosomes (the garbage disposal organelles within cells). It's thought that when lipofuscin accumulates to certain levels, it begins to negatively impact cell function, which eventually manifests in many age related conditions. Aubrey de Grey et al. have proposed that soil bacterial enzymes might have the capacity for degrading lipofuscin. It is proposed that humans might live as long as 1,000 years under the appropriate rejuvenative therapies. In 30 or 40 years, we'll have microscopic machines traveling through our bodies, repairing damaged cells and organs, effectively wiping out diseases. The nanotechnology will also be used to back up our memories and personalities and in 35 to 40 years, we basically will be immortal [53-57].

12. Fractal Models which are mathematical models used to represent fragmented geometry shapes :

Clever mathematical techniques are the foundation of increasingly realistic computer models and simulations. Now, math research is on the verge of creating tools that mathematicians hope will cut two ways: help scientists unlock explanations to many phenomena that remain mysterious and produce new modeling systems that could revolutionize product development and manufacturing. All this could be coming from fractals, those crinkly lines that look the same no matter how much they're magnified. "Fractal" is the term mathematicians use for patterns that repeat on all scales--like the spikes on a fern leaf that could be tiny copies of the fern itself [58 - 59]. Fresh research indicates that such recurring patterns may be more fundamental in nature than had been thought. If the new insights can be captured in fractal algorithms, science could gain extraordinary new powers. The same basic formulas could be "exploded" in scope to help scientists better understand large-scale systems such as the influence on climate from patterns of sunlight reflecting off the ocean's surface. And they could predict traffic flows on the Internet, or on physical highways. Conversely, "imploding" the formulas would adapt them for small-scale use, such as the behavior of molecules. That could save time in research & development by pointing out which avenues are more promising. Designers and engineers could update near-perfect models to speed their work on new products and processes [60-61].

13. Space travel for everybody :

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The earthly challenges facing humanity are the result of our heavy demand on resources and raw materials. Many of these materials can be found in space but the expense to extract them is a major barrier. In addition to cost, other obstacles to developing space are safety, reliability, and performance. According to the National Space Society there are four reasons why we need to pursue space exploration and colonization. These reasons—survival, growth, prosperity and curiosity—all point to the fact that we, as a species, want more room. Space exploration will give us a means to monitor the health of our planet, a source of resources and an outlet for our imagination. Using carbon nanotubes to make the cable needed for the space elevator, a system which could significantly reduce the cost of sending material into orbit. Nanotechnology will create the ability for humans to operate in space more safely. Applications where nanotechnology will impact space exploration are propulsion fuels, coatings, structural materials, smart uniforms, electronics and life support environments. These will be more efficient, stronger, self-healing and lighter than what is currently available [62-65].

IV. STRATEGIES FOR MANAGING THESE TECHNOLOGIES

Nanotechnology breakthroughs are expected to change the present lifestyle to a greater extent. The general purpose nature of nanotechnology and its advantages in solving both basic and advanced problems in all realm of society including, scientific, engineering, agricultural & food, medical & biomedical, building materials, electronics, cleaner air & water, renewable energy & storage, consumer products, automobiles & space technology, defense, and civil & mechanical engineering manufacturing will provide opportunity to find optimum solutions to many problems in the society. The anticipated breakthroughs in nanotechnology as central technology along with its related technologies like Optical Computation, Embedded Intelligence, Chameleon Chips, Flying cars, Immortality through nano-bio-technology, Space travel and other independent technologies like HIV Antivirus, Pseudo Senses, Off Planet Production, Protein Maps, Customized Kids, and Fractal Models will eradicate poverty & deceases in the society and fuel to the development of advanced homogeneous society completely different thinking and lifestyle compare to present day society.

Optical Computing will bring faster computers, better storage and communications, advanced artificial intelligence, and simpler ways of interfacing new software and hardware – including connecting radical new applications from machines directly with our bodies. One day, possibly by the end of 21st century or sooner, it will be possible to merge computer programs into our dreams. Computer-assisted dreaming could enable us to create dreams that we could share with others. Interactive shared dreaming could become a popular leisure pursuit.

Similarly the anticipated breakthrough in off-planet production in micro-gravity may provide new varieties of plants, new structures & colour combinations of flowers, new breed of seeds

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and even new community of animals and such possibilities will provide new opportunities in further research in science & technology as well as in business processes & industries. This will definitely effect the life style of human beings in terms of solutions to both basic needs and advanced comforts. The people in the society may get more varieties of products and services to make their life more happy and comfortable.

Similarly the anticipated breakthrough in decoding of the human genome and producing artificial proteins through protein mapping will provide opportunity of discovering artificial food and curing many cruel deceases of human being which may lead to hungry-less and decease free, happy and comfortable society. "If we live 20 more years, probably, we may never die". How new technology break through might play out in human life in the process of improving happiness and comfort during 21st century resulting from new innovations in above 13 areas. Nearly all diseases will become curable during this period; replacing aging and worn body parts will become common practice leading to immortality. By the end of 21st century it is believed that, most adults will look forward to a radically increased lifespan with near-perfect health.

As the global economy continues to be transformed by new technology breakthroughs, a keen competition will develop for talent, intellectual property, capital and technical expertise. Many of these factors responsible for shaping how nations compete, interact and trade. Technical innovations will increasingly shape economies and market robustness. Technology will continue to drive global and domestic development. Competition will be fueled increasingly by fast breaking innovations in technology and its adoption. If the proliferation of present technologies to form new business models is any indication of the speed and power of change in the economy, future technology breakthroughs will make for an even more dramatic paradigm shift. The evolution of a techno-economy, as contrasted with the petro-economy of today, is an intriguing idea. Anticipated technology innovations yet to come will set the timeline for this economic transformation. These technology breakthroughs may become integrated into industries and may become an embedded component of new products.

The social acceptance of these technology breakthroughs depends on Geographical Parameters like location, demography, culture, class, etc., Economic Parameters like the market penetration for the technology, its demand etc., Psycho-Social Parameters like people view on given technology, Affective Parameters like comfort level, Cognitive Parameters like awareness of those technologies, Technical Administrative Parameters like process of regulatory measures, Political Parameters like ability to debate, contention and organized opposition to a technology. This also include normative and quasi-normative parameters for the social acceptability of such technology breakthroughs like Religious Acceptability, Cultural Acceptability, and Ethical Acceptability of the effects and consequences of the penetration of

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these technologies. Managing these technologies by identifying crucial development stages in each case and nurturing such developments at laboratory level by means of creating awareness and incubation of minor and major discoveries through all possible support by means of effective decision making in all stages of technology development is essential.

V. CONCLUSION

The thirteen most anticipated breakthrough technologies predicted in this review are expected to substantially affect the human life in the society during the present century. The predicted discoveries and innovations in Nanotechnology and its six related technologies mentioned in technology breakthrough model and other six independent technologies listed in the model are expected to make drastic changes in everyday life of human beings in the world. From high power & speed computers to space travel, from chameleon chips to flying cars, from embedded intelligence to immortality, solutions to basic problems like food, pure drinking water, renewable energy, health & shelter for everybody, and clean environment through nanotechnology will change the lifestyle of the people. Other independent technologies listed in the model like HIV antivirus, pseudo senses, off-planet production, protein maps, customized kids, and fractal models are also helps to solve many problems of the society and support to solve many other problems. These breakthroughs are expected to create a new community of people called "super-tech-people" with modified social status. This will lead to development of new community without any partiality based on race, religion, country- origin, caste and even gender. The anticipated technology breakthroughs are change all the human beings as god who is ubiquitous, omnipotent and immortal. These breakthrough technologies certainly effect the religious, social, economical, political, cultural and ethical roots of the countries and supports the developments of a new heterogeneous generation as global citizens. Managing the minor and major discoveries in these areas through proper strategy is essential to support collective achievement of expected goal.

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